

ISic1033

I.Sicily inscription 1033

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list of

magistrates

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8718

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ἐπ]ὶ Ἡρα[κλείου τοῦ δαίνα]
2. Ἀρτέ[μιτικαί---]
3. γυμνασ[τάρχου---]
4. Ἀρχέδα[μος---]
5. Νυμφῶ[δῶρου---]
6. [Π]ολύκλ[ειτος---]
7. [τοῦ δαίνα]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492661

EDCS 39102187

PHI 140512

PHI 175420

PHI 175626

Bibliography

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